

ISic3094

I.Sicily inscription 3094

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645442

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 36.0865

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Orsi, P. 1895. Insigne epigrafe del cimitero di S. Giovanni in Siracusa. *Römische Quartalschrift für christliche Alterthumskunde und für Kirchengeschichte*. 9: 299-308. At 520 no.266

Ferrua, A 1946-1947. Florilegio d'iscrizioni paleocristiane di Sicilia. *Rendiconti della Pontifica accademia romana di archeologia*. 22: 227-239. At 231 no.6

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